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EFFECTS OF SOIL SALINIZATION ON SEED GERMINATION AND PHENOTYPIC VARIABILITY IN *PHASEOLUS VULGARIS* L.

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Abstract

Soil salinization negatively affects crop growth and productivity, with legumes like *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. being particularly sensitive. This study evaluated the “Yerli piyada” cultivar under salinity stress in field and laboratory experiments. Seed germination and fluctuating asymmetry (FA) of leaf width were measured, showing that higher salinity reduced germination and increased FA. These results highlight FA as a sensitive indicator of plant tolerance and developmental stability under salt stress.

Keywords: fluctuating asymmetry; seed germination; *Phaseolus vulgaris* L.; salinity stress.

Introduction.

Soil salinization is recognized as one of the most widespread and critical environmental stress factors affecting agriculture in Azerbaijan and worldwide. Areas affected by salinity are steadily increasing, posing a serious threat to sustainable crop production. Saline soils, with high concentrations of soluble salts, create osmotic stress, disrupt nutrient uptake, and negatively affect plant water relations, limiting growth, development, and productivity [2; 3].

Salinity stress induces physiological, biochemical, and morphological changes in plants, including reduced germination, impaired seedling establishment, stunted vegetative growth, and altered leaf and root development. The severity of these effects depends on salt concentration, plant species, developmental stage, and environmental conditions, posing a challenge to crop yields and food security [1;7;13;14;19;22].

Assessing salt tolerance among plant species is therefore a priority in agronomic and ecological research, helping identify tolerant genotypes and develop salt-resistant cultivars. This is especially important for legumes like *Phaseolus vulgaris* L., which are sensitive to salinity and essential for human nutrition. Studying plant responses at phenotypic and morphometric levels, including fluctuating asymmetry, provides insights into developmental stability under stress. Methods such as fluctuating asymmetry analysis allow researchers to quantify subtle deviations in plant morphology, reflecting the degree of developmental instability caused by environmental stressors [4; 5; 6].

This study aims to determine changes in the ecobotanical traits of the “Yerli piyada” cultivar of *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. under salinity stress and evaluate its developmental parameters using morphometric indicators.

Materials and methods.

The research object was the “Yerli piyada” cultivar of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.), belonging to the genus *Phaseolus* L. Experiments were conducted under both laboratory and field conditions. In the field and model experiments, soils with relatively

low salinity were considered as controls, whereas soils with relatively higher salinity were regarded as risk-prone saline soils. For field trials, the control site was located in the Khachmaz district, while the saline-risk sites were in the villages of Ceyranbatan and Mehdiabad in the Absheron district. Geographical coordinates of all experimental plots were recorded using a GPS navigator.

In laboratory-based model experiments, commercially obtained fertile forest soil was used as the control. Salinity of the control soil was artificially increased to 0.2% and 0.3% NaCl to simulate saline-risk conditions. Soil pH was determined in aqueous solution using a potentiometric method with an Orion 3-Star Benchtop pH Meter (Thermo Scientific, USA). Soil salinity was assessed by measuring the electrical conductivity of soil samples using an Orion 3-Star Benchtop Conductivity Meter (Thermo Scientific, USA) [12; 15; 20].

Seed germination percentage was calculated using the appropriate formula. Assessment of individual plant developmental stability was carried out using the fluctuating asymmetry method [8; 9; 10]. Measurements were performed on 30- and 60-day-old plants, focusing on a single morphometric trait: the maximum width of the leaf measured from the central vein to the right and left sides. Data obtained from these measurements were processed using the specially designed statistical software “STATISTICA 6”. Based on formulas, the bilateral difference (BF), fluctuating asymmetry coefficient (FA), and variance (D) were calculated [16; 17; 18; 21].

Results and discussion.

Soil analysis revealed significant variation in salinity and pH levels across the studied regions. In the soil sample collected from the Khachmaz district, electrical conductivity was measured at 2.72 mS/cm with a pH of 6.87. In contrast, the soil sample from Mehdiabad (Absheron district) exhibited a salinity of 14.99 mS/cm and a pH of 7.58. The highest salinity was recorded in the soil sample from Ceyranbatan (Absheron district), where electrical conductivity reached 46.2 mS/cm with a pH of 7.64. In the model experiments, the control soil

sample showed a salinity of 16.09 mS/cm with a pH of 5.70. When salinity was artificially increased, the soil treated with 0.2% NaCl exhibited an electrical conductivity of 19.99 mS/cm and a pH of 7.04, while the soil treated with 0.3% NaCl showed a salinity of 21.79 mS/cm and a pH of 7.61. Thus, the highest salinity concentration was detected in the soil sample obtained from Ceyranbatan (Absheron district), whereas the lowest salinity level was observed in the sample from the Khachmaz district.

The results show that:

- In field experiments, germination was highest in the control soil from Khachmaz (92%), moderately reduced in the more saline soil of Mehdiabad (80%), and lowest in Ceyranbatan (62%), indicating strong inhibition under higher salinity.

- In model experiments, germination remained high in control soil (92%) and was only slightly reduced under 0.2% NaCl (90%), but declined more sharply at 0.3% NaCl (76%), confirming the sensitivity of *Vicia faba* seeds to salt stress.

These findings demonstrate that increasing salinity negatively affects seed germination, with stronger inhibition observed in naturally saline soils compared to controlled low-level NaCl treatments.

The analysis of FA indicators in plants grown under different field conditions revealed distinct variations between control and experimental sites. In the control site (Khachmaz district), the mean BF of 30-day-old plants was 2.100 ± 0.182 mm, with D value of 2.132 and FA coefficient of 0.023. After 60 days, these values slightly decreased: BF to 1.986 ± 0.167 mm, D to 1.334, and FA to 0.016, indicating greater morphological stability in the control conditions.

In contrast, plants from Mehdiabad settlement showed a higher BF at 30 days (2.229 ± 0.198 mm) and substantially increased dispersion (3.165), though their FA value (0.020) was similar to the control. By day 60, BF decreased slightly to 2.043 ± 0.174 mm, while dispersion increased to 2.563 and FA doubled to 0.041, suggesting stronger developmental instability under these conditions.

The most pronounced differences were observed in Ceyranbatan. At 30 days, BF reached 2.914 ± 0.28 mm, considerably higher than both control and Mehdiabad plants, with a dispersion of 3.136 and the highest FA (0.051) among all groups. After 60 days, BF remained high (2.900 ± 0.281 mm), with further elevated dispersion (3.201) and a reduced but still notable FA (0.022).

Overall, the comparison shows that plants in the control site (Khachmaz) maintained lower levels of fluctuating asymmetry and dispersion, reflecting more stable growth conditions. In contrast, experimental sites—particularly Ceyranbatan—exhibited greater morphological variability and developmental instability, which may be associated with stronger environmental stress factors.

In the model experiments, the fluctuating asymmetry parameters of plants grown on control soil and salt-amended soils demonstrated clear differences depending on salinity levels and plant age.

For 30-day-old plants in control soil, the mean BF was 2.357 ± 0.214 mm, with D of 3.014 and a very low FA coefficient of 0.005, indicating stable growth under non-stressful conditions. When 0.2% NaCl was added, BF decreased slightly to 2.257 ± 0.020 mm, while D increased to 3.247 and FA rose to 0.020, suggesting the onset of stress-related developmental instability. At a higher salt concentration (0.3% NaCl), BF dropped further to 2.086 ± 0.180 mm, accompanied by elevated D (3.140) and the highest FA (0.027) among 30-day plants, showing a strong negative effect of salinity on early plant development.

In 60-day-old plants, similar trends were observed, though with some variations. In control soil, BF was 2.014 ± 0.171 mm, with low D (1.409) and FA (0.016), again confirming stable development in the absence of salinity stress. At 0.2% NaCl, BF increased to 3.200 ± 0.317 mm, D rose sharply to 4.372, and FA reached 0.030, indicating considerable morphological instability under moderate salinity. In plants grown with 0.3% NaCl, BF was 2.586 ± 0.242 mm, with intermediate D (2.924) and FA (0.024), suggesting that high salinity reduced growth but still caused notable instability.

Conclusion.

The results of field and model experiments demonstrated that fluctuating asymmetry (FA) is a sensitive indicator of plant developmental stability under environmental stress. Elevated FA values in plants from saline soils, particularly under moderate NaCl levels, reflect reduced stability and growth suppression. These findings confirm that FA can serve not only as a bioindicator of ecological stress but also as a practical tool for evaluating plant tolerance and adaptive capacity to salt stress.

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